

Technical Supportive Information

This supplement includes supportive information to the manuscript

Web-based collaborative model development in interdisciplinary consortia: design principles and practical guidance

by

Marvin van Aalst^{1†}, Alienor Lahlou^{2†}, Tanvir Hassan¹, William Gaultier², David Coliaux², Anna Matuszyńska^{1,3*}

¹Computational Life Science, Department of Biology, RWTH Aachen University, Worringerweg 1, 52074 Aachen, Germany.

²Paris Research, Sony Computer Science Laboratories, Paris, France.

³Center for Computational Life Sciences, RWTH Aachen University, Worringerweg 1, 52074 Aachen, Germany.

† These authors contributed equally to this work.

* Corresponding author: Anna.Matuszynska@cpbl.rwth-aachen.de

1 Case study 1: Web-interface ODE-based modelling tool

This case study emerged from a collaborative research consortium on microbial networking ([CRC 1535 – Microbial networking – from organelles to cross-kingdom communities](#)), in which synthetic microbiologists, microfluidic groups, cell biologists, and a computational modelling team worked in parallel on shared experimental systems. Models were developed alongside ongoing experiments, and new hypotheses emerged frequently as data accumulated across scales and platforms. As a result, assumptions about growth, interactions, and dynamics were repeatedly revisited, placing sustained pressure on how models were exchanged and discussed across disciplines. To account for these rapid changes, we began **deploying work-in-progress** ordinary differential equation (ODE) models through a lightweight, browser-based interface ([mxlweb](#)). ODE models remain a central formalism for describing dynamical processes in biology [1], and therefore are often the first point of contact between experimental collaborators and mechanistic modeling during a project. Providing experimental collaborators with direct access to evolving models changed how modelling supported experimental work. Partners could immediately identify where model behaviour aligned with or deviated from experimental intuition [Figure 1](#). These explorations **helped prioritise new experiments**, exposed implausible dynamics early, and generated concrete questions that directly informed subsequent model refinement. In turn, this feedback strengthened the iterative cycle of prediction, experimentation, and model updating, tightening the coupling between mechanistic modelling and experimental design within the consortium.

1.1 Technical implementation

The `mxlweb` app runs natively in the browser and does not require any backend. Its source code is freely available on GitHub at <https://github.com/Computational-Biology-Aachen/mxl-web> and an example deployment is also directly hosted via GitHub pages at <https://computational-biology-aachen.github.io/mxl-web/>. The app itself is implemented using the `svelte` ECMAScript framework (<https://svelte.dev/>) which allows generating a reactive frontend. The numeric integration calculations are being performed by the `scipy` library (<https://scipy.org/>) which has been compiled to WebAssembly using `Pyodide` (<https://pyodide.org/en/stable/>). Alternatively, the user can select to use supplied native ECMAScript function for integration. Further web-native integration backends are planned as well, but not currently implemented. To allow a smooth user interface and concurrent calculations of multiple analyses, a pool of web workers is used to perform the calculations.

The system of ODEs here is described as the product of the stoichiometric matrix N and the vector of reactions v , $Nv = x$, as is common in metabolic modelling. We further allow to derive quantities from other quantities like variables or parameters

Tripartite population dynamics

Dynamic model of a tripartite population of Public consumers, Cheaters and Private consumers.

Model equations

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dP}{dt} &= r_p P - \alpha P C - \beta P M - \eta P^2 \\ \frac{dC}{dt} &= \alpha P C - \nu C^2 \\ \frac{dM}{dt} &= r_m M - \beta M P - \gamma M^2\end{aligned}$$

(a)

Initial conditions & settings

Initial conditions

Public: 1 Cheaters: 1

Private: 1 Simulate until t: 100

Public (P)

r_p (growth rate): 0.4 η (density): 0.0001

Cheaters (C)

ν (density): 0.00001

Private (M)

r_m (growth rate): 0.2 γ (density): 0.0001

Interaction

α (P-C cooperation): 0.0002 β (P-M competition): 0.0001

(b)

(c)

Fig. 1 Browser-based interaction with evolving ODE models in mxlweb. (a) Web interface with model equation and description. (b) Slider controls for parameters, initial conditions, and simulation time to run simulations in the browser. (c) Simulation output showing subpopulation concentrations over the time.

and reactions. All these quantities are editable, with derived variables, stoichiometries and reactions being described by trees of MathML (<https://www.w3.org/Math/>) elements that can thus be easily mapped to SBML. Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the MathML editor as currently implemented, that allows editing and replacing each node arbitrarily. Common kinetic rate laws are pre-defined for convenience, but the editor also allows construction of any other arbitrary MathML tree to increase flexibility.

Template: Michaelis-Menten (e0)

Symbol Variable placeholder **Number** Constant value **Divide** Two-part fraction **Multiply** Multiply **Add** Add

Equation builder

k_{cat} \times e_{0} \times S $/$ k_M $+$ S

Tip: click any element to select it, then choose a MathML element above or adjust its value.

Preview

$$\frac{k_{cat} \cdot e_0 \cdot S}{k_M + S}$$

Fig. 2 Interface allowing to edit an equation tree. Each node can be edited or replaced by another MathML node. A live \LaTeX preview of the equation is given reactively below the editor. For convenience, common rate laws like mass action or Michaelis-Menten kinetics are pre-defined and can be selected above.

Models can be analysed using pre-defined routines like time course and steady-state simulations. Further, mxlweb supports running comparative analyses between

Fig. 3 Comparative analyses of competing model variants. The sliders above the models allow to dynamically adjust both parameters shared between models or ones that only occur in one of them. The time courses plotted below react dynamically to changes, enabling quick exploration of the model behaviour.

two model variants, shown in Figure 3. This allow to quickly compare competing hypotheses while being able to still modify shared parameters. Currently, these have to be defined by the user prior to deployment, but a dashboard allowing users to choose analyses on the fly is currently being developed.

2 Case study 2: web-based fluorescence modelling tool

The second case study arose in a different but complementary context during a European project (DREAM). Experimental data acquisition [2] led to discussions between experimentalists and theoreticians to derive a model of chlorophyll fluorescence. Here, the central challenge was not the dissemination of existing models, but the rapid evolution of model structure itself as new data were generated and interpreted with both experimentalist and modellers participating in collaborative work sessions. Initially, modifications to the model structure occurred in dense code and changes could not be tracked easily. This was problematic when a particular model fitted the data well at one point, but if following changes degraded the performance, there was no simple way to recover the former, better, configuration. Once a model was considered adequate, the codes were exchanged through Github which was challenging for non-specialist users.

The platform [ModelXplorer](#) addressed this issue by building on the existing code used to fit the data, without altering its computational structure. Instead of modifying variables directly in dense source code, parameters and model equations that had previously been hard-coded were exposed through a graphical interface, allowing the experimentalists and modellers to interactively edit them (Figure 4). All model runs, including model equations, parameter values, and generated traces are logged in a secure database following a framework initially developed to track evolution of Machine Learning models [3]. Models explorations can then be replayed in an interactive manner. Since the experimental runs can be considered as sensitive data, one partner hosts the services on a private server and provides secured access to partners.

The platform was proven useful in our experimentations where we allowed a larger range of exploration since we had less fear of loosing the 'good' configuration of the model. It also allowed for an alternative modelling approach where we designed the model by only entering a subset of ODE equations, and fitting it on data where the biological phenomena at play were limited to this subset of equation (eg. a mutant

lacking a response described in a supplementary equation). This allowed to evaluate the fixed and variable parameters on each equation separately and build the final model by bricks.

The screenshot shows a web-based interface titled "System". At the top, there is a text input field containing the differential equation: $dX_0/dt = k_{st}(a_0 - X_0) + X_0(L \cdot s_k - k_{stn})$. A green checkmark icon in the top right corner indicates that the equation is valid. Below the text box, there is a small input field for $X_0 =$ with the value "X0" entered. A blue button labeled "Get params" is positioned below the equation. Underneath, the equation is displayed in LaTeX format: $\frac{dX_0}{dt} = X_0 \cdot (L \cdot s_k - k_{stn}) + k_{st} \cdot (-X_0 + a_0)$. The interface is divided into several sections: "Fixed params" with inputs for a_0 (1.2), k_{st} (0.0139), and k_{stn} (0.0172); "Variable params" with an input for s_k (0.00817); "PFD Definition" with inputs for "flash" (1000), "light" (1), "dark" (0), and "PFDts" (100,890,800); and "Fluo Definition" with an input for "sol[;:0]".

Fig. 4 Interface allowing to enter a set of equation with fixed and variable parameters (indicated by \$), and to enter the values. Possibility to add an external perturbation (here called L for light). Choice in the display of the output to be plotted, here the fluorescence.

2.1 Technical implementation

The tool we propose is split into a backend part and a frontend both coded in Python. The source code for the app is available at <https://github.com/SonyCSLParis/ModelXplorer>. On the front-end, we have a web-based Graphical User Interface based on Dash framework (Figure 4).

2.2 Entering the equations

In a text box, it is possible to edit the equations of the model. The variables of the model should be named X_0, \dots, X_N for a model with $N+1$ variables. The model's equations also have 2 types of parameters, the fixed parameters designated by any combination of characters and the ones used for the estimation. To flip from fixed to variable, the user adds a \$ sign in front of the parameter. Once the model equations are entered in the text box, the user can extract parameters by clicking on the dedicated button. This action also checks whether the entered system is valid, indicating success with a validation icon in the top right corner of the text-box or displaying a cross if errors are detected. Then, the parameters of the equations, both fixed and estimated are available for setting their values in two columns on the interface. These values will be used as fixed values for the fixed parameters and as an initial value for the estimated parameters. The set of equations is automatically displayed as Latex text to ease reading, and is saved to be transferred to the database. Currently, the system can accept a set of ODEs but no additional analytical relationships between variables.

In our case study, we also needed to add an external perturbation which is encoded for our needs (light excitation protocol) and should be modified or removed for external use.

The user can run the model with the parameters entered and directly visualize the output in a graph embedded in the interface (Figure 4). The user can select how many

runs are displayed and the normalization method. The user decides which variable evolution to show in the "Fluo definition" section, allowing to probe individually the variables for debugging.

2.3 Fitting data

The front-end also allows to load and filter data samples on which the parameters will be estimated (Figure 5). It is easy to then switch between a parameter estimation mode and a model exploration mode in which new values can be tested for the various parameters. The backend automatically initiates the fits by solving for X_0 given the entered parameter, which allows manual trial-and-error initialization through preliminary model runs.

Fig. 5 Plot interface where the results are shown, whether they are obtained from running the model with parameters entered or fitting the model. It is possible to manually import data to be fitted, and to select the normalisation strategy (divide or subtract by the mean or value of the first point)

2.4 Storage of the runs

For every run or fit, the data is automatically sent to a MongoDB database relying on the Sacred infrastructure [3], which collects the outputs, the parameters, but also the source code and the packages version. The results can be visualized in a web interface compatible with the Sacred infrastructure (Omniboard, Figure 6). This systematic and automated storage strategy allows to navigate through past explorations and to recover sets of equations and parameters from particular fits covered during the exploration.

2.5 Deployment

To facilitate the use of the application, one partner can set-up a server where the app is running and provide secured access to other partners. We provide a Dockerized container to install the Database Management Strategy (MongoDB), the database visualization interface (Omniboard) and the app itself. The deployed service can then be exposed on a public domain following the partner's IT practices. Then, secured accesses can be established by filtering IP addresses of project partners and adding a secured login.

Fig. 6 Visualisation of the database content

References

- [1] Song, H.-S., Cannon, W.R., Beliaev, A.S., Konopka, A.: Mathematical modeling of microbial community dynamics: a methodological review. *Processes* **2**(4), 711–752 (2014)
- [2] Lahlou, A., Orlando, M., Bujaldon, S., Gaultier, W., Israelievitch, E., Hanappe, P., Le Saux, T., Jullien, L., Colliaux, D., Bailleul, B.: Interplay between high-energy quenching and state transitions in *chlamydomonas reinhardtii*: a single-cell approach. *bioRxiv*, 2025–01 (2025)
- [3] Greff, K., Klein, A., Chovanec, M., Hutter, F., Schmidhuber, J.: The sacred infrastructure for computational research. *SciPy* **17**, 49–56 (2017)